

Assessment Sheet

Organization:	
Participants:	

A. Product Knowledge		Answer (tick one for each question)	Importance of activity (5 = crucial 1 = unimportant)	Importance for completeness (5 = crucial 1 = unimportant)	Notes / comments
A1	How do you keep track of which type of products are maintained and/or used?	<input type="checkbox"/> We don't do this. <input type="checkbox"/> We do this in an ad-hoc way based on individual's own initiatives. <input type="checkbox"/> We know how we do this, but we do it in different ways in different teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We have defined processes for this that are common to all teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We collect experience and/or metrics from our approach and base improvements on that.			
A2	How do you keep track of which third party OSS and COTS components are included in maintained products?	<input type="checkbox"/> We don't do this. <input type="checkbox"/> We do this in an ad-hoc way based on individual's own initiatives. <input type="checkbox"/> We know how we do this, but we do it in different ways in different teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We have defined processes for this that are common to all teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We collect experience and/or metrics from our approach and base improvements on that.			
A3	How do you keep track of which version of third party OSS and COTS are used in maintained products?	<input type="checkbox"/> We don't do this. <input type="checkbox"/> We do this in an ad-hoc way based on individual's own initiatives. <input type="checkbox"/> We know how we do this, but we do it in different ways in different teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We have defined processes for this that are common to all teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We collect experience and/or metrics from our approach and base improvements on that.			
A4	How do you keep track of the possible threats that the products are facing?	<input type="checkbox"/> We don't do this. <input type="checkbox"/> We do this in an ad-hoc way based on individual's own initiatives. <input type="checkbox"/> We know how we do this, but we do it in different ways in different teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We have defined processes for this that are common to all teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We collect experience and/or metrics from our approach and base improvements on that.			
A5	How do you make specifications for products including usage, operating environment, and end-of-life?	<input type="checkbox"/> We don't do this. <input type="checkbox"/> We do this in an ad-hoc way based on individual's own initiatives. <input type="checkbox"/> We know how we do this, but we do it in different ways in different teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We have defined processes for this that are common to all teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We collect experience and/or metrics from our approach and base improvements on that.			
B. Identification and monitoring of Sources					
B1	How do you determine which external sources you should use to identify vulnerabilities?	<input type="checkbox"/> We don't do this. <input type="checkbox"/> We do this in an ad-hoc way based on individual's own initiatives. <input type="checkbox"/> We know how we do this, but we do it in different ways in different teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We have defined processes for this that are common to all teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We collect experience and/or metrics from our approach and base improvements on that.			
B2	How do you receive and follow up vulnerabilities reported to you by external parties?	<input type="checkbox"/> We don't do this. <input type="checkbox"/> We do this in an ad-hoc way based on individual's own initiatives. <input type="checkbox"/> We know how we do this, but we do it in different ways in different teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We have defined processes for this that are common to all teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We collect experience and/or metrics from our approach and base improvements on that.			
B3	How do you monitor sources of vulnerabilities? And with what time interval?	<input type="checkbox"/> We don't do this. <input type="checkbox"/> We do this in an ad-hoc way based on individual's own initiatives. <input type="checkbox"/> We know how we do this, but we do it in different ways in different teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We have defined processes for this that are common to all teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We collect experience and/or metrics from our approach and base improvements on that.			
C. Evaluating Vulnerabilities					
C1	How do you evaluate and decide the relevancy of identified vulnerabilities?	<input type="checkbox"/> We don't do this. <input type="checkbox"/> We do this in an ad-hoc way based on individual's own initiatives. <input type="checkbox"/> We know how we do this, but we do it in different ways in different teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We have defined processes for this that are common to all teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We collect experience and/or metrics from our approach and base improvements on that.			
C2	How do you decide on how to handle relevant vulnerabilities?	<input type="checkbox"/> We don't do this. <input type="checkbox"/> We do this in an ad-hoc way based on individual's own initiatives. <input type="checkbox"/> We know how we do this, but we do it in different ways in different teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We have defined processes for this that are common to all teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We collect experience and/or metrics from our approach and base improvements on that.			
D. Remedy of Vulnerabilities					
D1	How do you handle vulnerabilities that need urgent changes?	<input type="checkbox"/> We don't do this. <input type="checkbox"/> We do this in an ad-hoc way based on individual's own initiatives. <input type="checkbox"/> We know how we do this, but we do it in different ways in different teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We have defined processes for this that are common to all teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We collect experience and/or metrics from our approach and base improvements on that.			
D2	How do you handle vulnerabilities that are updated in a planned release?	<input type="checkbox"/> We don't do this. <input type="checkbox"/> We do this in an ad-hoc way based on individual's own initiatives. <input type="checkbox"/> We know how we do this, but we do it in different ways in different teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We have defined processes for this that are common to all teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We collect experience and/or metrics from our approach and base improvements on that.			
D3	How do you handle vulnerabilities that need no changes?	<input type="checkbox"/> We don't do this. <input type="checkbox"/> We do this in an ad-hoc way based on individual's own initiatives. <input type="checkbox"/> We know how we do this, but we do it in different ways in different teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We have defined processes for this that are common to all teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We collect experience and/or metrics from our approach and base improvements on that.			
E. Delivering Updates					
E1	What process is used to apply upgrades and patches to active products used by customers in the field?	<input type="checkbox"/> We don't do this. <input type="checkbox"/> We do this in an ad-hoc way based on individual's own initiatives. <input type="checkbox"/> We know how we do this, but we do it in different ways in different teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We have defined processes for this that are common to all teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We collect experience and/or metrics from our approach and base improvements on that.			
E2	What process do you have to protect the integrity of the patches when they are delivered to products?	<input type="checkbox"/> We don't do this. <input type="checkbox"/> We do this in an ad-hoc way based on individual's own initiatives. <input type="checkbox"/> We know how we do this, but we do it in different ways in different teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We have defined processes for this that are common to all teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We collect experience and/or metrics from our approach and base improvements on that.			
F. Communication					
F1	How do you communicate internally when vulnerabilities are identified and resolved?	<input type="checkbox"/> We don't do this. <input type="checkbox"/> We do this in an ad-hoc way based on individual's own initiatives. <input type="checkbox"/> We know how we do this, but we do it in different ways in different teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We have defined processes for this that are common to all teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We collect experience and/or metrics from our approach and base improvements on that.			
F2	How do you communicate externally when vulnerabilities are identified and resolved?	<input type="checkbox"/> We don't do this. <input type="checkbox"/> We do this in an ad-hoc way based on individual's own initiatives. <input type="checkbox"/> We know how we do this, but we do it in different ways in different teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We have defined processes for this that are common to all teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We collect experience and/or metrics from our approach and base improvements on that.			
F3	How do you communicate with media when vulnerabilities occur?	<input type="checkbox"/> We don't do this. <input type="checkbox"/> We do this in an ad-hoc way based on individual's own initiatives. <input type="checkbox"/> We know how we do this, but we do it in different ways in different teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We have defined processes for this that are common to all teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We collect experience and/or metrics from our approach and base improvements on that.			
F4	How do you communicate with your important customers about critical vulnerabilities?	<input type="checkbox"/> We don't do this. <input type="checkbox"/> We do this in an ad-hoc way based on individual's own initiatives. <input type="checkbox"/> We know how we do this, but we do it in different ways in different teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We have defined processes for this that are common to all teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We collect experience and/or metrics from our approach and base improvements on that.			
F5	How do you inform your customers about the patching status of products?	<input type="checkbox"/> We don't do this. <input type="checkbox"/> We do this in an ad-hoc way based on individual's own initiatives. <input type="checkbox"/> We know how we do this, but we do it in different ways in different teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We have defined processes for this that are common to all teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We collect experience and/or metrics from our approach and base improvements on that.			
F6	How is security-related information delivered with patches and new versions of your products?	<input type="checkbox"/> We don't do this. <input type="checkbox"/> We do this in an ad-hoc way based on individual's own initiatives. <input type="checkbox"/> We know how we do this, but we do it in different ways in different teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We have defined processes for this that are common to all teams/products. <input type="checkbox"/> We collect experience and/or metrics from our approach and base improvements on that.			